

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
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EBT Acceptance Note for **TEBT-2024-0008**

Submission Title	Systematic Review Methods in Environmental Health: a critical interpretive synthesis to inform the evolution of systematic review guidance
Submission Reference	TEBT-2024-0008
Handling Editor	Olwenn Martin ORCID: 0000-0003-2724-7882
Number of Reviewers	2
Submission Type	Single-Stage Study
Preprint DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11459414
Status	Accepted
Evaluation Date	06 December 2024
Evaluation Round	Editorial review round 2
Recommendation	Accept
Handling Editor's Explanation for Recommendation	The authors comprehensively have addressed concerns expressed by peer reviewers regarding the few elements of the methods and results that required clarifications.

Acceptance note

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor Olwenn Martin after 1 round of revision in response to 1 round of editorial triage and 1 round of peer-review.

During triage, the handling editor identified minor issues with the clarity of the research objective and the transparency of the reported methods the initial submission. It was deemed that these could be resolved following peer review, and the manuscript was advanced to peer-review.

During peer-review, the evaluators did indeed identify the issues above. They recommended that further details are needed to document methods and results more transparently. The authors addressed these issues by revising the methods to improve the clarity and transparency including adding a terminology section, providing further supplementary data and a more complete description of critical interpretative synthesis.

The following points of scientific interest were surfaced by the review process; purposive sampling and critical interpretative synthesis are somewhat unusual methods for use in systematic review in environmental health and more detailed descriptions of these methods improved legibility and transparency for our intended readership.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at [10.5281/zenodo.11660480](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11660480).